

MASTERY OF PLOT AND COMPOSITION IN THE PROSE OF ZH. MURATBAYEV

Sh.A. Aldongarova

Karakalpakstan Branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Karakalpak Research
Institute of Humanities

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the works of J. Muratbayev, a prominent representative of Karakalpak literature and writer, "Dygyryk" and "Shezhyrenyn shybygy". The writer's mastery of plot and composition construction is analyzed. The content, composition, and plot types of works are determined.*

Keywords: *"Dygyryk" "Shezhyrenyn shybygy," composition, plot, chronicle plot, types of concentric plot.*

Introduction

After our country gained independence, humanity's mindset changed, and its worldview developed. As developments in various spheres of social life elevated the spiritual world of society, a person's interest in their history and national values, as well as their worldview, expanded. Interest in our history has begun to manifest itself noticeably, especially in fiction.

One of the writers who contributed to the new artistic development of modern Karakalpak prose is Zhubatkan Muratbayev. His works are distinguished by their deep artistic analysis of national historical memory, time and human destiny, and complex spiritual connections between society and the individual. Plot structure and compositional mastery play a crucial role in the artistic world of the writer's prose. The dynamic plot, dynamic composition, and harmonious interweaving of events and time serve as the main artistic tools in revealing Zh.Muratbayev's characters' nature and depicting their inner spiritual waves. Therefore, analyzing the writer's individuality in plot and composition creation is an important scientific task in recognizing their literary method and poetic explorations.

Zh. Muratbaev's novel "Dygyryk" published on the eve of independence, artistically depicts the Turkestan period of the Karakalpak people. The depiction of events in the novel, for example, the participation of the Karakalpak people in the construction of the mausoleum of Ahmad Yassavi in Turkestan, as well as the fact that they moved due to the war of the Bukhara khan, the image of Sasyk biy is given through a consistent chronological plot. "In some cases, all life material can be presented in chronological order based on small scenes, without linking it to a single plot direction. If the plot is created in this way, it is called a chronicle plot" [1. P 86]. However, the author does not fully discuss the origin of the name Sasyk biy, why it was called "budoy." This, in our opinion, does not correspond to historical reality. When reading this work for the first time, it is natural to ask why the people called it "Sasyk biy." However, since this is a work of art, it can be created in conjunction with the author's artistic imagination.

Although the writer's works have many characters, there is a common idea or fateful principle that unites them all. Each supporting character is aimed at revealing the character of the main character and deepening the story. Zh.Muratbayev ensures the natural development of the plot by showing the character in action, revealing character through dialogue, and effectively using

internal monologue. Secondary events are also closely connected with the main storyline and maintain compositional integrity.

The choice of plot type for a literary work depends on the writer's creative style and artistic skill. A writer's artistic skill includes not only their figurative use of words but also their conciseness in describing events and phenomena, and their ability to use words concisely and effectively. This is one of the main criteria for a chronicle plot. "In a chronic narrative, the "artistic time" of a work can be expanded as much as desired: in it, the possibilities of depicting events occurring in parallel time, using the method of retrospection - the method of looking back from time - are quite wide. Furthermore, in a work built on a chronicle plot, elements outside the plot can naturally incorporate the author's thoughts into the artistic text" [2, P 103]. In the first part of the novel named after the writer Zh. Muratbayev, entitled "Blue Horizon," the participation of the Karakalpak people in the construction of the Khoja Ahmed Yasawi Mausoleum by Amir Timur in Turkestan is artistically depicted with historical evidence.

The novel focuses more on conveying historical information accurately to the reader than on the writer's artistic imagination. For example, "Through this caravan route, in 922, Ahmad Ibn Fadlan set out from Baghdad with a great purpose, carrying three thousand camels and leading five thousand people"[3, P 9] The Arab Caliph, al-Muqtadir, would instruct the caravan leader to conduct trade, establish diplomatic relations, and bequeath the Islamic faith, leaving scholars to teach children in the lands they visited. The events in this part of the novel are presented in chronological order. In the exposition section of the novel, the national coloring characteristic of the Karakalpak people is reflected (the flowering of the land after the harsh winter, the people's engagement in agriculture from the end of the 19th century, the depiction of true Karakalpak foods such as *turak*, *zharma*, and *kovurmash*, etc.). After this, the events of Amir Timur's arrival in Turkistan and his meeting with the Karakalpak tribes, from the beginning to the completion of the mausoleum's construction, are depicted with a chronological plot.

Literary scholar Z. Ktaybekova, in her dissertation, states: "This type of plot allows for a significant expansion of the story genre, thereby enabling the detailed depiction of events and phenomena, natural scenes, and the actions of humans and even animals"[4, P 83] This, in turn, contributes to the creation of complete and impactful artistic images," and analyzes the role of the chronic narrative in the development of the short story genre. The writer describes the unique characteristic of the Karakalpak people as follows: "As if neighbors were migrating to their neighborhood, their wives baked bread in the tandoor, their grandparents played with their grandchildren, engaged in their daily household chores, and seeing a people untouched by the enemy's sword, Temirlan, dragging his feet with quick steps, approached Sayitxo'ja Imam, who was reciting the Quran at the grave of Khoja Ahmad Yassaviy, and stretched out his right leg to sit on his knees"[3, p 5]. In these lines, the writer has deeply revealed the courage and human qualities inherent in our people through national values.

In Zh. Muratbayev's work "The Branch of the Genealogy," which depicts the history of the Karakalpak genealogy, historical sources such as the origin and formation of Karakalpak tribes and the emergence of our people as a nation are found. For this reason, the author refers to their work as such. "Because the genealogy passed down from father to son, from son to grandchild and great-grandchild, and became an inheritance for subsequent generations"[6, p 116] said scholar K. Mambetov in his work.

Despite Zh. Muratbayev being a veterinarian by profession, creating such valuable works on the history of the Karakalpak people is itself a great skill. The writer's frequent conversations

with livestock owners must have played a role in this. Literary scholar K. Mambetov expresses the following opinion on this matter: "Hence, most of his life was spent among shepherds. The spiritual world of shepherds is inextricably linked with the history of the people"[6, p 117]. Indeed, after the majority of our people engaged in animal husbandry, the events they experienced were not unfamiliar to them. It would be accurate to say that the writer was greatly influenced by the fact that most of them were attentive and inclined to tell stories. But not all the stories I've heard can be called history. "Nevertheless, not all the events in this book can be considered true historical facts. Although the Karakalpaks were known as a large tribe in the 9th century, it cannot be considered that all their clans were formed during that period"[6, p 120] scholar K. Mambetov expresses critical opinions. However, the writer's creation of such a valuable literary work based on the materials and information he/she has researched was itself an achievement.

The writer's compositional mastery is often manifested in the use of psychological parallelism. Scenes of nature, details of the material world, combined with the character's mood, become artistic symbols of their inner world. The artistic detail adds fresh momentum to the plot development and reveals changes in the character's inner world. This approach enhances the emotional power of the writer's prose. The plot of this work by Zh. Muratbayev is built on a more concentrated plot. This is because it focuses primarily on reality, not on temporal sequence like a chronicle plot. The work depicts the arrival of the Arab ambassador Ibn Fadlan to the land of the Karakalpaks and the fact that he gathered a considerable amount of information from the people based on interesting events. Based on folk legends and tales, the origin, division, and naming of the Karakalpak tribes are extensively discussed and depicted with artistic imagination.

Ibn Fadl was astonished that the unity, sincerity, and mutual trust of the Karakalpak people were skillfully revealed through a conversation with the village elder. For example: "The ambassador conversed with the city's elder about its history, traditions, and way of life, recording many unknown news in his travel journal. Ibn Fadlan was amazed by the strength of the Karakalpak unity and their loyalty to their kinship, refusing to intermarry or become in-laws until they reached seven generations. He has strong faith in his wives. The ambassador was amazed to see the women and men working together in unity and firm confidence. Indeed, our ancestors have always placed great importance on respect, reverence, and trust for women. Comforting Muratbayev constructed the dialogue naturally and sincerely. During the story, the character's personality, worldview, and internal contradictions are revealed. The author's narration and the character's words find harmony, forming a compositional unity. The writer masterfully revealed this in this work.

In some places, the author reinforces the psychological content of the work by introducing internal monologue and free narrative forms. Comforting Muratbayev constructed the dialogue naturally and sincerely. During the story, the character's personality, worldview, and internal contradictions are revealed. The author's narration and the character's words find harmony, forming a compositional unity. In some places, the author reinforces the psychological content of the work by introducing internal monologue and free narrative forms. Furthermore, the remarkable humility of Turganbay Ishan, a renowned son of the Karakalpak people, is revealed through dialogues with the ambassador:

-Dear Ambassador, my faith does not permit me to make you and myself sinful before God by speaking incorrectly about history. In this precious time of conversation with you, I want to hear kind words of advice only from you. "If I quench my spiritual thirst for the reward of your

respected words, who have recognized the righteous path, I will see myself in the land of happiness," said Turg'anboy Eshon, showing great humility before the envoy Ibn Fadlan.

-God does not allow one person to dominate another. Even a bird soaring high is a child of the earth. God's wrath descends upon one who writes lies and gives advice. Only a believer who listens to the scholars of the people and praises the truth will be forgiven by God. "Therefore, it's best for me to listen to you today" said the envoy, indicating his readiness to capture every word Turganbay Ishan uttered.

Thus, Turg'onboy Ishan, hoping for forgiveness if there were any shortcomings in his words, began to speak and recount the Karakalpak genealogy. Thus, as can be seen from this, we can understand that the Karakalpak people have long been attentive to words and eloquent. The mastery of plot and composition construction in Muratbayev's prose is one of the main aesthetic indicators that defines the writer's artistic world and reveals his creative individuality. The author's poetic system is distinguished by his artistic mastery of life material, as well as his psychological analysis aimed at revealing the deep inner layers of human existence. These features are comprehensively reflected in the structure of the plot and composition. Thus, the writer, with a certain degree of artistic imagination and historical data, tells the story of the formation of the Karakalpak people. The writer's artistic skill is clearly evident in his works. Especially in revealing characters and depicting events, they portray them through their unique writing style.

The complexity of compositional structure is another clear sign of Zhubatkan Muratbayev's prose. Representing the categories of time and space in ways such as returning to the past, a system of memories, and the intersection of parallel lines gives the work a multi-layered character. Such approaches not only enrich the story but also aim to reveal the character's spiritual world and historical memory. Maintaining the internal integrity of the composition, the author thoughtfully coordinates the connections between episodes, transforming each scene into a structural element bearing an ideological load.

Conclusion

Additionally, the works of Zhubatkan Muratbayev extensively reflect topics such as national historical memory, connection between society and individual, love for homeland, and the significance of spiritual values. These themes are clearly visible not only at the content level but also in the artistic structure of the plot and composition. The author's approaches to the artistic mastery of historical memory are one of the important steps in reviving the traditions of national literature. In conclusion, the writer Zh. Muratbayev made a great contribution to the development of Karakalpak literature, especially Karakalpak historical novels, through his prose works.

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